

Microbiological Assessment of Liquid Herbal Medicines Sold in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The global use of herbal medicines has increased, emphasizing the need for quality assurance. A study in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, analyzed herbal liquid samples using microbiological techniques. Twenty (20) samples were collected from different locations. Bacterial counts in different areas ranged from 1.86×10^6 to 520×10^6 cfu/ml, while fungal counts ranged from 3.1×10^5 to 7.2×10^5 CFU/ml, the results showed no statistically significant differences between the average scores of the five groups (p -value = 0.42). Bacteriological and fungal analysis involved various agar media and culturing methods, resulting in the identification of six bacterial species (*Bacillus marinus*, *Bacillus insolitus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratiaspp*, and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*) and three fungal genera (*Penicillium marneffeii*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Phialophora parasiticum*). *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus spp*, and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* were the most frequently isolated bacteria. The majority of samples exceeded the recommended range for bacterial and fungal counts, posing a risk according to Public Health Laboratory Service guidelines for liquid herbal drugs. To prevent food-borne infections, continuous monitoring and adherence to standard compliance measures are crucial for ensuring the safety and quality of herbal medicines along the streets.

Keywords: Bacterial counts, global use, herbal medicines, microbiological analysis, quality assurance

1.0 Introduction

Ancient cultures have long traced the origins of herbal medicine, which encompasses the therapeutic application of various plant components, including stem bark, leaves, and roots, aimed at treating ailments and promoting overall health and wellness [1]. The overarching goal of herbal medicine is to restore the body to a state of equilibrium, facilitating self-healing processes [2,3]. Different plants exert distinct effects on various physiological systems, with commonly used herbs such as garlic, ginger, neem, guava, and mango plants providing traditional remedies for specific ailments [1, 3].

The global popularity of herbal medications, particularly in Nigeria, continues to grow steadily

owing to their perceived natural and safe characteristics [4]. This perception of effectiveness, safety, and reduced adverse effects compared to conventional drugs contributes to the widespread usage and accessibility of herbal pharmaceuticals [5]. The increase in herbal medication use correlates with the prevalence of illnesses such as AIDS and drug-resistant malaria [5, 6].

One significant factor driving the increasing popularity of herbal remedies is the high cost of healthcare consultations and conventional medications [7]. This trend is supported by advances in packaging materials and heightened public awareness through traditional medicine trade fairs [7, 8]. Additionally, the presence of NAFDAC registration numbers on registered herbal products likely boosts their usage in Nigeria

[8]. Despite the prevalent sale and consumption of liquid herbal remedies in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, there is often inadequate oversight and control regarding their microbiological standards.

In Nigeria, natural prescriptions and related items often enter the market without mandatory health or toxicological assessments and lack routine evaluation by regulatory bodies to ensure manufacturing practices and quality standards [9]. The continuous availability of these natural items to consumers without prescription increases the risk of contamination with pathogenic microorganisms, posing serious health hazards such as gastrointestinal illnesses and infections [10]. Since the plant materials used to make herbal medicines are good for microbe growth, it is very important to check the microbiological quality of liquid herbal medicines in Birnin Kebbi to make sure they are safe and follow the regulatory rules.

This study aims to evaluate the microbiological quality of liquid herbal medicines sold in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Specific objectives include determining the total aerobic bacterial and fungal counts in the samples, identifying pathogenic bacteria and fungi, and assessing the frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates across different collection locations.

This study's findings provide valuable insights into the microbiological quality of liquid herbal medicines in Birnin Kebbi, informing regulatory authorities and the public about potential health risks associated with consuming contaminated herbal products. Such information can guide the development of appropriate quality control measures and regulations to ensure the safety of liquid herbal medicines in the region.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Area of study

Birnin Kebbi is a city located in Northwestern Nigeria. It is the capital city of Kebbi State and the headquarters of the Gwandu Emirate. The location of Birnin Kebbi is 12.45° North Latitude and 4.2° East Longitude. Kebbi State covers a geographical land area of 36,800 km², bordering the nation of Niger Republic to the west and Benin Republic to the southwest. The Nigerian States of Niger, Sokoto, and Zamfara border it to the south, north, and east, respectively. It contains Sudan and Sahel Savannah vegetation. Birnin Kebbi is a big town in Nigeria, with an estimated 366,200 population [11].

2.2 Collection of sample

Twenty (20) liquid herbal medicine samples were randomly collected from five different retail outlets within the Birnin Kebbi metropolis: Kebbi central market, Haliru-Audu Road, Sultan Abubakar-Saudana Road, Bayan Kara, and Badariya Road. The samples were taken to the laboratory immediately for bacterial and fungal analysis within 24 hours.

2.3 Bacterial and fungal analyses

The herbal samples were analysed using standard microbiological methods according to [12] for the bacterial and fungal isolates [13].

2.4 Preparation of samples

Ten millilitres (10 ml) were measured from each liquid herbal sample and diluted in a beaker containing 90 ml of sterile distilled water.

2.5 Preparation of culture media

All media were prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions and we re-sterilised in the autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. The media used for this study were nutrient agar, saubraux dextrose agar (SDA), mannitol salt agar (MSA), eosinmethylene blue agar (EMB), and MacConkey agar (MA).

2.6 Serial dilution of Herbal samples

One millilitre (1 ml) was pipetted from the stock sample and added to a blanked test tube of 9 ml of peptone water, making a dilution of 10⁻¹. Next, was the dilution to the second, third, fourth, fifth, and sixth diluents (10⁻², 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴, 10⁻⁵ and 10⁻⁶).

2.7 Inoculation of Herbal samples

For this study, one millilitre (1 ml) of the second, fourth, and sixth dilutions (10⁻², 10⁻⁴, and 10⁻⁶) was poured onto nutrient agar plates one at a time so that bacteria could be studied. These plates were then incubated at 37°C for a duration of 48 hours. Similarly, for fungal analysis, the same volume was pour-plated onto Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) or Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) plates and incubated at 28°C for a period ranging from 3 to 5 days. Each sample was inoculated onto the petri dishes in duplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the results.

2.8 Bacterial and Fungal count

Bacterial and fungal colonies on agar plates were counted using a colony counter system, which detects and counts colonies based on size, shape, and colour, minimising human error and increasing efficiency.

2.9 Gram Staining

The procedure commenced by applying a droplet of sterile distilled water to a clean slide that was free of oil. Subsequently, a wire loop used for inoculation was subjected to a flame until it reached a red-hot temperature, and subsequently allowed to cool. A minute fraction of the colony was meticulously selected and applied to the droplet of water on the slide. After the slide had been air-dried, it underwent a gentle heat fixation process using a flame. Afterwards, the smear was treated with a 1% crystal violet solution and left undisturbed for 1 minute before being rinsed with distilled water. Afterwards, Gram iodine was used as a mordant for a duration of 1 minute, and the excess was then removed. The slide underwent a 30-second treatment with 70% alcohol, functioning as a decolorizer, followed by rinsing with distilled water. Following these procedures, the slide was immersed in a counter stain solution, safranin, for a duration of 1 minute. It was then rinsed with distilled water and let to dry in the air. Finally, the slide was examined under the microscope with an oil immersion $\times 100$ objective lens. As observed by [12], Gram-positive organisms exhibited a purple coloration, and Gram-negative species displayed a red coloration.

2.10 Isolation of Bacteria

The presence of *Escherichia coli* was determined by subculturing bacterial isolates on Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB) agar plates using the streak method, followed by incubation at 37°C for 48 hours. Positive samples exhibited a characteristic greenish metallic sheen, which is indicative of *Escherichia coli*.

Mannitol salt agar was employed for *Staphylococcus aureus* detection. Pure bacterial isolates from nutrient media cultures were aseptically subcultured onto sterile Mannitol Salt Agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Yellow colonies were presumptively identified as *Staphylococcus aureus*.

To differentiate between gram-negative lactose fermenters and non-lactose fermenters,

MacConkey agar was utilised. Pure bacterial isolates from nutrient media cultures were inoculated onto MacConkey agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Lactose fermenters, such as *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella*, produced red colonies surrounded by a zone of precipitated bile, whereas non-lactose fermenters, such as *Salmonella* and *Shigella*, appeared as colorless or transparent colonies. Further identification of colonies was conducted using biochemical tests [14].

2.10 Biochemical Test

The biochemical tests for the identification of the isolates were citrate utilization, coagulase, indole, methyl-red, Voges-proskauer, triple sugar iron (TSI), urease, oxidase, and catalase tests. The method of [12] procedures were used for these biochemical tests. These series of biochemical tests were used to identify isolated colonies of *Bacillus insolitus*, *Serratia* spp and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* from the nutrient agar base on their reaction to distinctive metabolic properties.

2.11 Fungi Identification

The fungal cultures were checked for their morphological characteristics such as colour, texture, edge and form.

2.12 Microscopy Identification of fungi

This study used microscopy to identify fungi by looking for spores and conidia and determining whether they were septate or aseptate. A drop of lactophenol blue solution was placed on a clean, grease-free glass slide. Subsequently, a sterile needle was used to extract a small portion of the fungal culture from the periphery, which was then gently teased into the lactophenol blue solution. The resulting smear was covered with a cover slip and examined under a microscope, utilising both 40x and 100x objective lenses for detailed observation.

2.13 Statistical Analysis

The experiments were conducted in duplicate. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's post-hoc analysis for multiple comparisons between samples ($n = 20$). Statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism 6 Software (San Diego, USA). Data were expressed as mean \pm SD and presented in both tables and bar charts.

Differences were considered statistically insignificant at a p-value of <0.05.

3.0 Results

3.1 Total Viable Counts of Bacteria isolated From Herbal liquid samples

Table 1 and 2 shows the bacterial and fungal viable counts of herbal liquid samples collected

from five (5) different locations within Birnin Kebbi. The average bacterial counts shown in Table 1 ranged between 1.97×10^6 CFU/ml to 520×10^6 CFU/ml. The fungal count ranged from 3.1×10^5 CFU/ml to 7.2×10^5 CFU/ml. There were no significant differences ($p=0.42 > 0.05$) in mean total aerobic bacterial counts across the locations.

Table 1: Average Bacterial counts in Herbal liquid sample in Birnin Kebbi

Samples	Location A	Location B	Location C	Location D	Location E
	Mean \pm SD 10^6 CFU/ml				
1	2.08 ± 3.0	1.86 ± 3.0	2.54 ± 0.03	87.0 ± 0.005	181 ± 3.0
2	1.97 ± 3.0	154 ± 3.0	158 ± 3.0	204 ± 3.0	95.0 ± 0.5
3	8.30 ± 3.0	133 ± 3.0	520 ± 5.0	233 ± 3.0	167 ± 3.0
4	670 ± 0.005	142 ± 3.0	95.0 ± 0.005	87.0 ± 0.5	67.0 ± 0.5

Key: Location A=Kebbi central market, B = Haliru Audu Road, D = Sultan Abubakar Saudana Road, D = Bayan Kara, and E = Badariya Road.

Table 2: Total viable fungal counts in Herbal liquid sample in Birnin Kebbi

Samples/Locations	1	2	3	4
A	3.1×10^5	4.3×10^5	4.1×10^5	3.3×10^5
B	5.3×10^5	-	6.1×10^5	-
C	-	3.6×10^5	7.0×10^5	6.2×10^5
D	5.6×10^5	6.6×10^5	-	6.8×10^5
E	7.2×10^5	5.8×10^5	4.1×10^5	-

Key: Location A=Kebbi central market, B = Haliru Audu Road, D = Sultan Abubakar Saudana Road, D = Bayan Kara, and E = Badariya Road.

**Total 3: Average Bacterial Counts (cfu/ml) of Herbal liquid samples from different locations
Anova: Single Factor**

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
	4	10	2.5	1.666666667
Location A	4	494700000	1.24×10^8	9.27496E+15
Location B	4	615000000	1.54×10^8	5.3625E+14
Location C	4	681490000	1.70×10^8	5.97547E+16
Location D	4	524870000	1.31×10^8	1.15342E+16
Location E	4	510000000	1.28×10^8	3.04633E+15

Key: Location A=Kebbi central market, B = Haliru Audu Road, D = Sultan Abubakar Saudana Road, D = Bayan Kara, and E = Badariya Road.

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	7.29669E+16	5	1.45934E+16	1.040570059	0.424277492	2.772853
Within Groups	2.52439E+17	18	1.40244E+16			153

Key: Data presented between groups and within group shows that p value is 0.42.

3.2 Identification of Bacterial Isolates in Herbal liquid samples

Table 4 shows isolation and biochemical characterization of six bacterial isolates from the herbal liquid samples. The bacterial isolates identified were *Staphylococcus aureus*,

Staphylococcus spp., *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*, *Bacillus marinus*, *Bacillus insolitus* and *Serratia spp.* Table 5 shows colony characterization and microscopic views of fungal isolates and the probable fungal isolates were *Penicillium marneffeii*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Phialophora parasiticum*.

Table 4: Characterization/Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Colonial morphology	Gram Rxn	Microscopic Examination	Biochemical Rxn							Suspected bacteria		
			Ind	MR	VP.	Cit	Mot.	TSI	Oxi		Cat.	Coa.
Large opaque, raised, irregular surfaced and non pigmented colony	+	Long rod appear in chains	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	<i>Bacillus marinus</i>	
Large opaque, raised, irregular surfaced and non pigmented colony	+	Long rod appear in chains	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	<i>Bacillus insolitus</i>	
Golden yellow and opaque colonies in NA.	+	Cocci in irregular grape like clusters	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Golden yellow and opaque colonies in NA.	+	Cocci in irregular grape like clusters	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Staphylococcus sp</i>
Flat circular Milky colonies.	-	Rods in short chains and pairs.	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	0	<i>Serratia sp</i>
Large opaque, raised, irregular surfaced and off white colony	+	Long rod appear long and filamentous in dispersed	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+		<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i>

Key: Rxn = Reaction, + = Positive, - = negative, Ind = Indole test, MR = Methyl Red test, Cit. = Citrate Test, VP=Voges-Proskauer, Mot = Motility Test, TSI=Triple sugar Iron, Oxi = Oxidase Test, Cat = Catalase test and Coa = Coagulase Test, NA=Nutrient Agar

Table 5: Colonial and Microscopic Characteristics of fungal isolates

Colony Characteristics	Microscopic View	Probable Mould
The colonies exhibited a flat, spreading morphology, displaying hues ranging from brown to black, characterised by a dense cottony surface and a cream-coloured reverse side.	It was observed that conidiospores have smooth walls and feature terminal verticils of metulae, with each metula bearing phialides. The conidia were characterized by a rough-walled structure and brown coloration.	<i>Penicillium marneffeii</i>
Colonies exhibited a flat spreading morphology, ranging in colour from brown to black, featuring a dense cottony surface and a cream-coloured reverse side.	The conidial heads exhibit a dark brown to black coloration, characterised by a radiate and biserate morphology, with metulae measuring twice the length of the phialides. The conidia are brown and possess a rough-walled texture.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
The cultures exhibited slow growth, displaying a suede-like appearance with radial furrows. Initially, they appeared whitish-grey, gradually transitioning to an olivaceous-grey hue as they aged.	The phialides were observed to be brown and characterised by thick walls, while the conidia appeared hyaline, exhibiting thin walls and a cylindrical shape.	<i>Phialophora parasiticum</i>

3.3 Distribution and Percentage Frequency of Bacterial Isolates

Table 6 and Figure 1 below, shows the frequency of bacterial isolates indicates that *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most common type of bacteria found in herbal liquid samples from Location A (35.72%). It was followed by *Staphylococcus* sp. (21.43%), *Bacillus insolitus* (14%), *Bacillus marinus* and *Serratia* spp. (10.71%), and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* (7.14%). In Location B, *Staphylococcus aureus* has the highest percentage of occurrence at 39.13%, followed by *Staphylococcus* sp at 17.39%, *Bacillus insolitus* and *Bacillus marinus* at 8.70% and 10.71%, respectively, and *Serratia* spp. and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* at 13.04%. At Location C,

Staphylococcus aureus is the most common type (31.57%), followed by *Staphylococcus* sp. (15.79%) and *Bacillus insolitus* (21.05%). *Bacillus marinus*, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*, and *Serratia* spp. are the least common types (10.53%). Location D records the highest percentage of occurrence (26.32%) for *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus* ssp, followed by *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* and *Bacillus insolitus* (21.05%), *Bacillus marinus* (10.53%), and *Serratia* spp. The bacteria that were most common in Location E were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus* sp., and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* (23.53%). They were followed by *Bacillus marinus* (17.65%), *Bacillus insolitus* (11.76%), and *Serratia* spp., which were not recorded.

Table 6: Distribution and Percentage Frequency of Occurrence of Bacterial Isolates in Herbal liquid samples

Organisms/ Sample	<i>Staphy. Aureus</i> (%)	<i>Staphy.spp.</i> (%)	<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i> (%)	<i>Bacillus marinus</i> (%)	<i>Bacillus insolitus</i> (%)	<i>Serratia spp</i> (%)
A	10 (35.72)	6 (21.43)	2 (7.14)	3 (10.71)	4 (14.29)	3 (10.71)
B	9 (39.13)	4 (17.39)	3 (13.04)	2 (8.70)	2 (8.70)	3 (13.04)
C	6 (31.57)	3 (15.79)	2 (10.53)	2 (10.53)	4 (21.05)	2 (10.53)
D	5 (26.32)	5 (26.32)	3 (15.78)	2 (10.53)	4 (21.05)	0 (00.00)
E	4 (23.53)	4 (23.53)	4 (23.53)	3 (17.65)	2 (11.76)	0 (00.00)

Key: Location A=Kebbi central market, B = Haliru Audu Road, D = Sultan Abubakar Saudana Road, D = Bayan Kara, and E = Badariya Road. % = percentage

Key: Location A=Kebbi central market, B = Haliru Audu Road, D = Sultan Abubakar Saudana Road, D = Bayan Kara, and E = Badariya Road.

Figure 1: Percentage frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates in herbal liquid samples

4.0 Discussion

The study conducted on the microbiological assessment of liquid herbal medicine sold in Birnin Kebbi provides a comprehensive examination of the microbial quality of herbal medicine samples procured from various sources within the study area. With the primary objective of elucidating the safety implications associated with herbal medicine consumption, this research endeavours to uncover potential risks and health

threats arising from microbial contamination. Due to the increasing prevalence of herbal remedies as alternative therapeutic approaches, understanding the microbiological characteristics of these products assumes paramount importance in safeguarding consumer well-being [15].

The findings from this study reveal alarming levels of microbial contamination in herbal liquid samples collected from various locations in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. The average bacterial count was

1.16×10^8 to 5.1×10^8 cfu/ml, and the average fungal count was 3.1×10^5 to 7.2×10^5 cfu/ml.

The one-way ANOVA results showed no statistically significant differences between the average scores of the five groups (p -value = 0.42). The lack of significant differences may be due to homogeneous demographics and a small sample size. The study provides insights into group performance and highlights the need for further research into influencing factors.

These levels significantly surpass the acceptable thresholds outlined by the World Health Organisation (WHO). According to WHO, United States Pharmacopoeia and European Pharmacopoeia guidelines, the total aerobic bacterial and fungal counts in herbal medicines should not exceed 10^5 cfu/ml [16]. This stark observation resonates with the aerobic mesophile counts documented in the study by [17] titled "Microbiological Analysis of Herbal Medicines Collected from Different Areas of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

The contamination of herbal samples with a multitude of bacteria and fungi, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Bacillus marinus*, *Bacillus insolitus*, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*, *Serratia spp.*, *Penicillium marneffeii*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Phialophora parasiticum*, raises serious concerns regarding public health. The findings regarding the frequency of bacterial isolates from different locations indicate that *Staphylococcus aureus* exhibits the highest occurrence rate at 39%, followed by *Staphylococcus spp.* at 26%. Furthermore, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* accounts for 23%, *Bacillus insolitus* for 21%, *Bacillus marinus* for 17%, and *Serratia spp.* for 13%. These results underscore the prevalence and distribution of various bacterial strains within the herbal medicine samples, providing valuable insights into the microbial landscape of these products and their potential implications for public health. *Staphylococcus aureus*, known for its association with foodborne illnesses such as toxic shock syndrome and scalded skin syndrome due to its ability to produce enterotoxins, poses a particularly high risk to consumers of herbal products, especially those with pre-existing medical conditions originally targeted for herbal remedies [18, 19]. Researchers [20] found links between *Bacillus* species, especially *Bacillus marinus*, and gastrointestinal illnesses with diarrhoea. These cases show how dangerous

contaminated herbal medicines can be for your health [17, 18].

Additionally, the presence of medically significant fungi, such as *Penicillium*, *Candida*, and *Aspergillus*, underscores the potential dangers, particularly to immunocompromised individuals, as these fungi can cause diseases and produce mycotoxins [21]. The detection of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* species in herbal remedies suggests inadequate drying processes, emphasising the urgent need for rapid drying to prevent significant growth and the production of harmful substances. These fungi's ability to thrive in low-water-content environments highlights the potential reduction in herbal medications' therapeutic efficacy [21, 22].

This study attributes the substantial microbial contamination to various factors such as soil quality, harvesting methods, drying procedures, handling practices, and storage conditions. Contaminants in non-sterile pharmaceutical items can compromise product effectiveness, posing significant risks to patients [16].

The statistical analysis (ANOVA) conducted on liquid herbal treatments indicates a marked discrepancy in microbiological quality, surpassing permissible thresholds, highlighting the urgent need for regulatory interventions and quality control measures in the production, distribution, and utilisation of herbal medicinal products in Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the microbiological quality of herbal medicines sold in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. The findings indicate that the total aerobic bacterial and fungal counts in the samples were significantly high, with pathogenic bacteria and fungi detected in a substantial proportion of the samples. Furthermore, the frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates varied across different collection locations, suggesting a potential link between the storage conditions and the contamination levels. These results highlight the urgent need for regulatory measures to ensure the safety and quality of herbal remedies in Nigeria. The lack of regulation surrounding these medications poses a significant risk of transmitting contagious diseases within the community, thus constituting a public health threat.

6.0 Recommendations:

Therefore, the government must closely monitor herbal medical products to ensure their production, preparation, and manufacturing adhere to high standards of quality. This will help reduce the potential risks to consumers and patients. We cannot overemphasize the importance of regularly monitoring and implementing strict quality control measures for herbal medical items manufactured, sold, and used in Nigeria. Maintaining a consistent quality level for herbal medical items, composed of intricate mixtures derived from biological sources, requires substantial effort. To maintain the composition and concentration of components in herbal medicinal products and ensure consistent therapeutic effectiveness, it is crucial to carefully choose plant materials and follow standardized production techniques. All stages of the production process, from the selection of propagation materials to the delivery of the completed product to the end user, must incorporate quality assurance.

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8.0 Conflicts of Interest

We declare that there are no conflicts of interest among the authors involved in this study.

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